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GENERAL AND LOCAL EFFECTS OF ORTHODONTIC BRACKET SYSTEMS ON THE BODY

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Annotation. This article comprehensively examines the effects of fixed orthodontic bracket systems on the morphological and functional status of dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues, and alveolar bone. Furthermore, it provides a scientific explanation of the potential causes of headache, temporary visual disturbances, and functional imbalance of the vertebral column following the placement of a bracket system.

Keywords: bracket system, posture, headache, vision.

Relevance: The dento-maxillary system has undergone significant changes during the course of evolution. This is directly related to changes in the human diet. This process is mainly manifested by a reduction in jaw length and the regression of the third molar. All of this leads to a lack of space for the eruption of permanent, and sometimes primary, teeth.

As a result, various types of malocclusion and anomalies in tooth alignment occur. The prevalence of dento-maxillary anomalies ranges from 11.4% to 71.7%, which is associated with differences in research methodology, the level of professional training of clinicians, and sampling (representativeness) errors [6].

Therefore, the use of orthodontic bracket systems to address these problems is considered highly relevant. However, bracket systems have not only positive but also negative characteristics. For this reason, it is necessary to study both their local and systemic effects, which would make it possible to minimize their disadvantages and maximize their advantages.

Research Objective: To study the effects of bracket systems on the dento-maxillary system, as well as the general changes occurring in the organism.

Research Tasks: 1. To investigate the impact of bracket systems on the spine and visual organs, and to explain the causes of headache occurrence. 2. To determine what changes occur in dental tissues, periodontal tissues, and bone tissue

Materials and Methods: An analysis of scientific articles, journals, and dissertations on this topic was conducted.

Results and Discussion: The correction of pathological occlusion types occurring in the upper and lower jaws, as well as abnormal tooth positioning, is one of the urgent issues in modern orthodontics. In the treatment of such anomalies, non-removable orthodontic appliances, particularly bracket systems, are widely used. However, after the installation of these appliances, some patients may experience complaints of a general nature. These include headaches, posture disorders, effects on visual acuity, as well as manifestations of astheno-vegetative syndrome.

The occurrence of these symptoms is explained by changes in craniosacral biomechanics arising under the influence of fixed orthodontic appliances [3]. All anatomical structures of the maxillofacial region are closely interconnected, forming a single morpho-functional system. There are complex functional relationships between the teeth, alveolar processes, temporomandibular joint, masticatory muscles, and cranial bones [6].

Therefore, the impact on one part of this system leads to adaptive responses throughout the entire dento-maxillary complex. When a bracket system is installed, specific compensatory processes are activated in the body. Orthodontic forces initially affect the teeth and dental arches, after which these changes are transmitted to the jaw bones, cranial structures, and cervical muscles. As a result, these changes may also influence the functional state of the spine [5]. Thus, the process of orthodontic treatment involves not only local changes but also complex biological and biomechanical alterations at the level of the entire cranio-cervical system.

Prolonged tension of the cervical and spinal muscles leads to changes in posture and contributes to the development of headaches. The pathogenesis of headache is associated with muscle strain: when the neck muscles become excessively tense, the scalp and facial muscles also undergo reflex tension. This condition results in episodes of “tension-type headache,” which are typically manifested by pain in the temporal and occipital regions of the head. Clinical studies show that muscle tension and changes in arterial blood pressure increase the intensity of headaches, especially under conditions of stress and psychological strain.

The integrated interaction between the dento-maxillary system, the shoulder girdle muscles, and the spine ensures the functional balance of the human body. Disruption of this relationship leads to changes in stabilometric parameters, displacement of the center of gravity, and, consequently, the development of postural imbalance. Postural disorders, in turn, increase the risk of orthopedic and neurological complications, including chronic strain in the intervertebral discs and cervical spine muscles. Thus, tension in the cervical and spinal muscles influences the development of headaches not only mechanically but also from a neurophysiological perspective.

Postural changes are observed in 71.4% of patients undergoing orthodontic treatment [3]. When bracket systems are installed in the dento-maxillary system, they affect not only tooth alignment and changes in the jaw joints, but also the processes of bone tissue remodeling in the areas of cranial sutures. During this process, excessive stretching of the lateral group of cervical muscles is observed,

which leads to mechanical compression of the external and internal carotid arteries. As a result, not only arterial blood flow but also venous outflow is impaired, causing brain tissues to remain in a state of prolonged ischemia.

Continuous oxygen deficiency contributes to the development of asthenovegetative syndrome. This syndrome manifests as rapid fatigue, difficulty concentrating, decreased memory function, and reduced overall intellectual performance. Studies show that such complaints are observed in 93.7% of patients with bracket systems [3]. In addition, vascular spasm and cerebral ischemia negatively affect the trophism of the optic nerves. As a result, 31.8% of patients experience a gradual decrease in visual acuity, which significantly impacts the normal functioning of the visual system [3]. Furthermore, after the installation of bracket systems, various adverse processes occur within the dento-maxillary system. These include changes in the hard tissues of the teeth, periodontal tissues, and alveolar bone tissue. The elements of bracket systems make it difficult to maintain proper oral hygiene, which leads to disturbances in the mineralizing and immunological functions of saliva [1]. At the same time, the function of dental plaque changes, microhemocirculation in periodontal tissues is disrupted [4], and both local and humoral immune responses, as well as the quantity of oral microflora, increase.

These conditions promote the accumulation of soft dental deposits, which subsequently increases the risk of dental caries development. In addition, procedures such as fixation and replacement of bracket system elements, acid etching of enamel, grinding, and polishing may lead to tooth hypersensitivity in patients. Prolonged hypersensitivity, in turn, can affect patient behavior, even resulting in the need for anesthesia before the simplest non-invasive procedures [3]. After the installation of bracket systems, oral diseases such as gingivitis and periodontitis may also develop. The progression of inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues is usually associated with poor oral hygiene during orthodontic treatment, improper selection of the orthodontic appliance, as well as the initial condition of periodontal tissues and hard dental tissues [2]. When bracket systems exert force on the dental arch,

deformation of the jaws occurs, accompanied by a complex and prolonged process of bone trabeculae remodeling. Bone resorption takes place in areas where teeth should not be positioned, while new bone formation occurs on the side toward which the tooth movement is required.

Bracket systems also have a certain impact on the condition of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ). After the installation of brackets, patients undergo an adaptation period to the new orthodontic appliance. During this period, unusual discomfort, excessive mechanical pressure on the dental arches, and hypertonicity of the masticatory muscles may often occur. Under the influence of orthodontic forces, the biomechanical balance between the teeth and jaw bones temporarily changes. This condition may lead to pain, discomfort, or joint sounds (crepitation) in the temporomandibular joint area during movement.

In addition, the quality of life of patients in the post-orthodontic treatment period is of great importance. The positive outcomes of treatment with bracket systems include restoration of the functional activity of the dento-maxillary system, improvement of aesthetic appearance, and the formation of an optimal morphological occlusion. However, in some cases, negative outcomes may also be observed. One of the most significant among them is relapse, that is, the gradual return of occlusion to its initial state.

The occurrence of relapse is explained by the fact that after the removal of the bracket system, the new position of the teeth is initially stabilized not by bone tissue, but by cartilage or connective tissue elements. The subsequent complete transformation of these tissues into bone tissue represents the final stage of orthodontic treatment. Therefore, the retention period after active orthodontic treatment is of critical importance, during which removable or fixed retainers are used. If the achieved results are not properly maintained, the outcomes obtained through long-term use of bracket systems may become unstable, leading to reduced treatment effectiveness..

Conclusion:

1. Bracket systems have both positive and negative effects on the dento-maxillary system as well as on the entire organism.

2. General changes are observed in the spine, including postural alterations, changes in cervical muscles, decreased vision, tension-type headaches, fatigue, and memory impairment.

3. Local effects are manifested by changes in dental tissues, periodontal tissues, and bone tissue.

4. According to the analysis results, if the patient strictly follows the doctor's recommendations during treatment with fixed orthodontic appliances and after their removal, it is possible to avoid the negative effects of bracket systems and achieve only positive outcomes.

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